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California State University, Fullerton
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NURSE DRIVEN ASSESSMENT OF MATERNAL-INFANT ATTACHMENT
IN THE NEONATAL INTENSIVE CARE UNIT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this project is to develop and implement an assessment tool for nurses to use to assess mother-infant attachment in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU). In this setting, the infant's medical needs often interfere with bonding behaviors. There was concern that nurses did not recognize attachment and bonding behaviors so that parents and infants exhibiting poor attachment could be referred to the psychologists in order to improve parental infant attachment. Training was provided to help nurses increase awareness of the characteristics associated with positive and negative behaviors of attachment. This training allowed the bedside nurses to notify the social workers and psychologists if any negative behaviors were noted. The goal of this project is to increase the number of referrals to the psychology team.

The Plan Do Study Act (PDSA) framework was utilized to guide this project. The assessment tool was piloted in Zone One of the NICU and inter-rater reliability was established. A 30 day pilot was conducted to evaluate the use of the tool. Once the 30 day pilot was completed, a survey was sent to the 125 nurses who were identified as working in Zone One during the pilot to determine nurses' opinion about the usefulness of the training on the attachment assessment tool.

The survey was completed by approximately 23% of the nurses who were sent the survey via email. There were 21 (91.3%) nurses who felt reported the education and training were adequate. There were 23 (100%) nurses who noted that the tool was easy to

use and that the information was applicable to their job. There were six (27%) nurses who knew about the psychologists, with seven (31.8%) somewhat familiar with their presence. There were nine (40.9%) nurses who were unaware of the psychologists being used in the NICU. Most of the nurses surveyed stated that the information gathered from the tool and from the education would assist them in initiating a referral to the psychology team (73.9%). Only two nurses stated that they would not be so apt to make a referral based on the information provided. The completion rate was low, however, this may have been the result of the survey being sent out by the nurse scientist. This was done in order to avoid any possible issues with coercion, since the project author was a nurse manager on the unit.

There were no referrals to the psychology team in Zone One prior to the pilot implementation. In contrast, there was an increase in the total NICU referral rate during the month following the project pilot. This may have been due to the increased familiarity with the protocol and increased confidence in making referrals.

An additional PDSA cycle will be initiated in an attempt to gain a better understanding of the maternal-infant attachment and the characteristics that can be associated with poor attachment. The psychologists are on board with assisting in educating the staff nurses and are hopeful that referrals will increase as nurses become more aware of attachment behaviors.

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BACKGROUND

According to VanderWeele, Lantos, and Lauderdale (2012), the rate of live preterm births in the United States of America rose from 11.2% to 12.8%, between 1989 and 2004, more than that of any other industrialized nation. Changes in obstetric practices, such as an increase in the use of fetal monitoring and advances in medical care of premature infants, are likely causes of this increase. In addition, advancements in technology and medicine have made it possible for premature infants born at 22 weeks gestation to survive. These very premature infants must be cared for in the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) for several weeks to months. Premature infants typically require ventilatory support along with several other modalities of care in order to survive, and they are at risk for a variety of long-term complications that range from mild to severely debilitating. Premature infants are at a greater risk for intracranial hemorrhage, due to hypoxic episodes and chronic lung disease due to surfactant deficiency. They also have feeding issues due to an inability to coordinate their suck and swallow reflexes. Extreme prematurity, even in the absence of complications may require an infant to remain in the NICU for an extended period of time (Gardner, Carter, Hines, & Hernandez, 2011).

Full-term newborns may experience adverse effects during the perinatal period and require admission to NICUs for stabilization or treatment of medical or surgical problems, some of which may be life threatening or have poor outcomes and require extensive hospitalization. Full-term infants who are admitted to the NICU may stay for prolonged periods of time, which is dependent on their diagnosis and the treatment that they may require. For example, an infant born with a congenital diaphragmatic hernia

may require surgery; however, they may be too unstable to tolerate it. Therefore, the infant must be maintained on Extra Corporeal Membrane Oxygenation (ECMO) to stabilize them prior to surgery. Due to the infant's unstable condition and use of an intensive intervention, the mother may not be able to hold or touch her infant, delaying the maternal-infant bond. The NICU environment is life-sustaining; however, prolonged hospitalization can create stress that will affect the development of healthy mother-infant relationships which can then negatively impact the infant's future physical and mental health (Feeley, Genest, Niela-Vilen, Charbonneau, & Axelin, 2016; Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016).

Multiple factors, such as the mother's physical contact either touching or holding her infant or talking to the infant, are critical to the success of the mother-infant relationship and its impact on infant mental health. Mothers of premature infants are especially vulnerable to depression or other negative mental health issues because they may perceive themselves as having failed in successfully carrying their child to term, though in most cases, preterm delivery is not the result of the mother's actions or negligence (Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016). Mothers who blame themselves may exhibit symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder, anxiety, and depression while coping with the challenges of parenting a premature infant (Gerstein, Woodman, Burnson, Cheng, & Poehlmann-Tynan, 2017). Although there are multiple assessment tools to ascertain the mental health of mothers, evaluation of the infant is more difficult.

Szaniecki and Barnes (2016) explored the challenge of measuring infant mental health and found that early recognition of issues and prompt intervention are key to assisting families to obtain a referral to a mental health specialist. One tool used to

measure infant development and mental health is the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit Network Neurobehavioral Scale (NNNS).

Although the tool is used with hospitalized infants, it cannot be used until the infant is medically stable in the NICU (Lester, Andreozzi-Fontaine, Tronick, & Bigsby, 2014). The NNNS tool can be used with preterm infants as well as full-term infants with conditions that require admission to the NICU. The tool is used primarily on high-risk infants and can be used to assess overall development, with special attention given to neurological and motor functioning.

Providers in a large NICU in a hospital in Southern California recently advocated for greater involvement of pediatric psychologists in the emotional and behavioral assessment and subsequent treatment of neonatal patients and the parent-infant dyads in their clinical setting. The focus was to identify family members who would benefit from consultation with a team of mental health specialists. Social workers notified psychologists each time they believed a patient and family should be referred for a mental health consultation. Since this intervention was a success in providing families with the mental health assistance that they required, psychologists now see all NICU patients and their families at some point during the NICU hospitalization.

Shortly after the project began, the group of psychologists sought out the project author, who is the nurse educator in the NICU. They asked that nursing join with them and take a more active role in identifying at risk infants and their caregivers. The psychologists and the project author agreed that the nursing staff in the project setting are in a unique position to identify early indicators of problems in the mother-infant dyad. A nursing assessment could be instituted focusing on mothers interacting with their infants.

NICU nurses care for infants 24 hours a day and are well suited in their role as neonatal nursing experts to vigilantly observe maternal-infant bonding when the mothers are in the NICU interacting with their infants. Furthermore, research demonstrates that high risk families of infants in the NICU benefit from early intervention aiding in increased bonding (Browne & Talmi, 2011; Fearon & Belsky, 2011; Gerstein et al., 2017).

A preliminary review of data evaluating the NICU's new mental health assessment protocol revealed that there was a gap in the timing of notification for referral to the psychology team. Additionally, nurses' documentation of the mother-infant interaction was unreliable due to inconsistent documentation as not all nurses were documenting the maternal-infant interaction. Despite the existence of a documentation field in the medical record for the nurse to note visitors, including mood or affect at the time of the visit and details of visitor interactions with the infant, maternal-infant exchanges were inconsistently documented in the EMR.

Problem Statement

In light of the fact that nursing assessment of maternal-infant bonding was not conducted or documented in a systematic fashion and given the need for a nurse driven assessment protocol to initiate referrals to social work and psychology for early infant mental health services, there was a need for nursing education, protocol development, and an evaluation plan for the nurses in the NICU. Along with key stakeholders in the NICU, the project author embarked on a quality improvement project to enhance the nurse's role in early intervention of infants and families who are at risk of mental health issues.

Purpose

The purpose of this DNP project is to develop and pilot a nurse driven tool to assess mother-infant dyad attachment in the NICU and evaluate its effectiveness. This was accomplished through attainment of the following objectives:

- Convene an expert panel, including psychologists, neonatologists, and nurses, to identify, operationalize, and evaluate reactions or interactions associated with the attachment process that the infant or mother display during maternal visits.
- Develop an assessment tool to document all infant reactions and maternal interactions during maternal visits using a paper and pencil tool.
- Create a nursing protocol for using the assessment and an algorithm for early psychological referral.
- Develop and conduct nurse education sessions regarding maternal-infant attachment and the newly developed protocol.
- Pilot the tool and collect reliability and outcome data.
- Evaluate the project through an EMR review to determine efficacy of the protocol in generating early infant mental health referrals. This will occur post completion of the DNP program.

Theoretical Framework

After identifying the need for a change or an improvement in practice, the next step is to outline a structured plan or guide to achieve the desired outcome. A theoretical framework outlines the necessary steps required to develop a change in practice or protocol and provides guidance throughout each stage of the project (Hall, 2016). Given

the nature of the project, the framework selected was the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycle which served as its framework.

The PDSA cycle describes a process that is used to determine whether a practice or a change may need to be improved (Deming, 1994, Hall, 2016). The PDSA cycle was originally used in business but was adapted for use in other occupations where it is a useful tool for continuous improvement (Deming, 1994). In health care, this model is effective for protocol development, quality improvement or a change in practice.

The PDSA model consists of four stages (Deming, 1994; Gillam & Siriwardena, 2013; Hall, 2016). The first stage is Plan, in which a team is established. The team should be comprised of the staff who regularly work in the area or facility. These are some of the stakeholders who have a vested interest in the common goal of quality improvement. It is the responsibility of the team members to develop a plan and initiate the process. In the development of the plan, the team must agree on a common objective or a measurable goal to determine whether their plan will be successful (Gillam & Siriwardena, 2013).

The second stage of the model is Do. During this stage, team members put the plan into action and monitor any issues or problems that arise (Hall, 2016). The objectives that were agreed upon in the planning stage are audited during this stage. Issues are documented, and the analysis of any problems will be noted in the third stage (Gillam & Siriwardena, 2013).

In the third stage of the PDSA model, called the Study phase, the team begins to study the work that had been completed (Deming, 1994). Data are collected and reviewed as the team studies the plan that has been implemented. During an analysis of the data the

team will ascertain as to whether the outcomes were as expected or if modifications are needed (Gillam & Siriwardena, 2013).

The final stage of the cycle is to Act. During the act stage the team determines what follows next (Gillam & Siriwardena, 2013). For example, if the data analysis of problems encountered during implementation reveals that the initial objectives are not being met a change in plan is required during this stage. It may be that based on the results of the analysis, no changes or improvements are needed. If that is the case, the decision to continue with the protocol or to complete the cycle again will be made (Deming, 1994).

Implementation of the Project PDSA Cycle

The PDSA model was used to guide a quality improvement project in the NICU at the project author's practice setting (see Figure 1). The project was termed the Nurse Driven Assessment of Maternal-Infant Bonding (NDA). During the plan stage, the author collaborated with an expert panel to review the various aspects of the project and the necessary tools, educational training and EMR changes to achieve the desired outcome. She also secured the required administrative permissions to conduct the project.

The next stage in the PDSA process that was undertaken in this project was to do or to carry out the plan. This stage included the implementation of the tool on the unit and collection of the data needed to affirm that the plan is in place and being followed as prescribed (Gillam & Siriwardena, 2013). The use of the tool was monitored for proper and accurate use; inter rater reliability testing to assure accurate use of the tool was undertaken with planned audits.

Figure 1. PDSA model (Deming, 1994, p 132).

Following implementation of the tool to assess mother-infant attachment behaviors, the next stage was to study (Gillam & Siriwardena, 2013). During this project stage, data collected (i.e., number of referrals to the hospital's psychology service) using the NDA tool underwent critical appraisal as to its value in guiding nurse driven referrals. The NDA and the protocol may need to be revised but this would occur if another cycle of the PDSA is determined to be necessary.

The last stage of this cycle is to act, which was not part of this DNP project; however, it will take place at a later date. All other components of the model up to the act cycle were reviewed as part of this project and necessary changes in the NDAT were suggested. When the act stage is convened and if the assessment tool requires revision, based on the initial roll-out and pilot, the expert panel will be reconvened and consulted (Gillam & Siriwardena, 2013). Their recommendations will be considered, and changes will be processed. Another cycle can be activated to allow for the optimal state to be

achieved for each of the changes that will need to be facilitated if the NDAT is to be fully implemented in the NICU.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Plan for Literature Review

The review of literature focused on the assessment of maternal-infant attachment and the identification of behaviors that characterize this bonding. Several databases were used as sources for evidence supporting the development of a maternal-infant assessment tool for use in the NICU setting. Selected databases included CINAHL, EBSCO, Google Scholar, PsychInfo and PubMed. Search terms included: infant/psychology, infant behavior, parent-child relations, mother-child relations, object attachment, bond*, attach*, neurobehavior, mental health, intensive care units, and neonatal.

A secondary search of the same databases was conducted with a focus on terms related to information about nurses' knowledge of maternal-infant bonding in the NICU or newborn nurseries. Search terms included: nurse, pediatric, pediatric nursing, nurse's role, nursing assessment, and NICU. Both searches were limited to peer-reviewed manuscripts published in English between 2009 and July 2018. Scholarly books, chapters, and seminal work published in the 1950s on the subject of maternal-infant attachment were also reviewed. Articles focused solely on maternal issues only without consideration given to infants were excluded.

A search of the AHRQ website and the website for Dr. W. Deming was conducted for information about the PDSA model used as a theoretical framework for this project. Permission to use his diagram or any other pertinent information was obtained (Appendix A). The same databases were used to search for literature about the use of the PDSA model in the clinical setting.

Introduction

During the past decade, infant mental health issues have been a topic of interest due to an increase in the number of young children and adolescents diagnosed with anxiety, depression, and/or disruptive behaviors (Fearon & Belsky, 2011; Gerstein et al., 2017; Pennestri et al., 2015). Early assessment of child mental health issues, beginning during infancy, enables the healthcare provider to expeditiously diagnose concerning behaviors and quickly refer for treatment. The literature review revealed instruments that can be used as early as the first, week of life to measure the characteristics of healthy socialization between mother and infant (Boukydis, Bigsby, & Lester, 2004; Brazelton & Nugent, 2011). This review of literature focused on one of the major components of mental health in the infant, maternal-infant bonding and attachment, instruments used to assess attachment, and the nurse's role in the assessment of the mother-infant dyad.

Attachment

Bowlby (1988) theorized that attachment was the ability of one person to become close with another person, not only in proximity, but also in relation to their personal bond. As a result, the two may continue to interact and further develop their relationship. Bowlby's seminal work has been studied since the development of his theory of attachment was initiated in 1951. His work began with the observation of the behaviors of infants and their mothers. He noted infant's behaviors such as sucking, clinging to the mother. He also noted behaviors termed as "signaling" such as crying or smiling, to which the mother responds (Bowlby, 1958).

The concept of secure attachment refers to an infant's ability to remain physically close to his or her caregiver, leading to a feeling of safety (Bowlby, 1988). Although

attachment may occur at any time, much of the research on attachment has been focused on the mother-infant bond (Browne & Talmi, 2011; Zelkowitz et al., 2011). After birth an infant typically remains close to the mother. The mother is usually the one who feeds, holds, and cares for the infant, thus promoting a secure bond between infant and mother (Bowlby, 1988). A mother diagnosed with a mental deficiency, mental health diagnosis, or physical illness may have difficulty in bonding with her infant. This may interrupt the formation of a secure attachment within the dyad and result in a state of detachment between mother and infant (Firestone, 2013; Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016; Shah, Clements, & Poehlmann, 2011). The infant may not feel secure with the mother when she visits the infant in the NICU and the infant may respond by showing signs of insecurity and detachment such as inconsolable crying, or eye contact avoidance (Bowlby, 1988).

Ainsworth (1978) expanded on Bowlby's theory by studying infants and children to determine if attachment was individualized with similar circumstances. Patterns of attachment for infants and children were examined to determine if differences in attachment occurred based on the situation. The Strange Situation Tool was developed to assess an infant or child's ability to cope with separation from their mother or caregiver (Ainsworth, Blehar, Waters, & Wall, 1978). Infants with a secure attachment to their mother were more likely to return to a secure state when reunited with her, whereas those without secure attachment exhibited negative reactions, such as crying and fussiness when reunited with their mothers. Research conducted by Bowlby (1988) and Ainsworth (1978) demonstrated the importance of the mother-infant bond and the consequences of inadequate attachment.

Maternal-Infant Attachment

Extensive research has been conducted on maternal-infant attachment (Fearon & Belsky, 2011; Feeley et al., 2016; Fleury, Parpinelli, & Makuch, 2014; Korja, Latva, & Lehtonen, 2012). A study conducted by Murray, De Pascalis, Bozicevic, Sclafani and Ferrari (2016) examined the mother-infant dyad's ability to "read" each other's behaviors and reactions. The mother must become attuned to her infant's needs in order to ensure that she is responding to the infant's responses; the infant must do the same in return. For example, the infant will react positively if the mother presents by smiling or cooing whereas, the infant may react negatively to a mother's harsh voice or angry looks (Murray et al., 2016). The mother will react positively to the infant's cues such as smiling by smiling back, cooing, and singing. On the other hand, if the infant is crying, the mother may either attempt to comfort the infant or turn away from the infant (Murray et al., 2016). The level of bonding will predict the mother's reaction to the infant's behavior.

Another study conducted by Phuma-Ngaiyaye and Kalembo (2016) reviewed the aspects of the maternal-infant attachment and the relationship between mothers and their nurses/nurse midwives while their infants were in the hospital. This qualitative, explorative study had a sample size of 10 mothers, and five nurses/nurse midwives. The study was conducted at a tertiary NICU in Malawi. The aim of the study was to determine the type of intervention that could lead to the support of the bonding process between mothers and their infants who had been admitted to the NICU. The researchers asked questions about the mother's perception of the support provided by the nurses and nurse midwives. As the nurses and nurse midwives were also participants, they were

asked questions regarding their perspective on how they assisted in developing the maternal-infant bond (Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016).

Phuma-Ngaiyaye and Kalembo (2016) concluded that the nurses and nurse midwives played an important role in supporting the maternal-infant bond. The mothers provided their infants with the physical care that the infants needed as they progressed in the NICU environment. The nurses and nurse midwives provided the mothers with the education, communication, and support that the maternal-infant bond required during the infant's hospital stay.

The purpose of a study by Flacking, Thomson, and Axelin (2016) was to gather information on the feelings of parents regarding closeness to their preterm infant during the infant's stay in the NICU. The researchers provided a tool of emotional closeness for a total of 23 parents of infants in the three separate NICUs.

Overall, themes that were noted were indicative of some action or participation in the care of the infant that allowed the parents to feel close to their infant. Such actions as breastfeeding, kangaroo care, holding and touching the infant were noted as important aspects of closeness. The parents also noted that the ability to be involved in the decision making and care of their infant was important in feeling close to their infant (Flacking et al., 2016).

The results of these three studies indicate that the maternal-infant bond is important and that nurses can facilitate the bond for the infant in the NICU. Mothers are encouraged by nurses to participate in the care and to physically touch and hold the infant. These types of behaviors by the mother can encourage the infant to respond in kind.

Cues Indicating Attachment

After the birth of her infant, a mother typically begins the process of physical attachment with her infant by holding the infant close, engaging in skin to skin contact, breastfeeding, stroking the face of the infant and placing the infant in the “en face” position. In this position, the mother holds her infant so that they are face to face and eye to eye. The mother will concentrate on her infant and talk to the infant, usually in a higher pitched voice to capture the infant’s attention (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011; Davidson, London, & Ladewig, 2008; Murray et al., 2016). These characteristic behaviors typically occur soon after the birth of an infant.

During the first weeks of the infant’s life, the mother will continue to speak to the infant, make eye to eye contact, smile, and coo (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011). She responds to the infant’s reactions by continuing these behaviors, which in turn will strengthen her attachment to her infant. Murray et al. (2016) conducted a longitudinal study of mothers’ reactions to their infant between the ages of one to nine weeks. The team recruited 20 mother-infant dyads and after consent was obtained, they visited the homes of their participants at weeks 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9. There, they videotaped the face-to-face interactions between mother and infant. The videotaped interactions demonstrated how the exchanges progressed over time. The researchers were able to see how the infants became more expressive and interactive over the course of the nine weeks. The observations confirmed that the maternal-infant attachment developed over time (Murray et al., 2016).

Immediately after a healthy infant is born, the infant is typically very alert. This is the optimal time for attachment to begin. The infant may be placed on the mother’s

abdomen or chest to begin skin-to-skin contact. As the infant remains with the mother, the infant will begin to communicate with the mother. According to Brazelton and Nugent (2011), the mother will begin to attach to her infant in what they refer to as the “neonatal moment of meeting” (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011, p. 98). The infant will exhibit behaviors such as turning to look and listen to the mother. The mother will respond to these cues psychologically by her interpretation that these are positive signs of attachment (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011).

Rubin (1967a) conducted a seminal study of pregnant women in an effort to determine how they acquired their ability to function as a mother. She studied both first time mothers or primiparas and multiparas or mothers who had already given birth to one or more children. Rubin and her team completed interviews and observations to gain insight into these mother’s abilities to develop their role as a mother and how this occurred. An important aspect of the study included the concept of “taking-in”, in reference to how the mother assimilated and accepted the infant into her role as a mother. There were instances where the mother would find similarities with her infant and a member of her family, whether it be the father or a sibling of the infant. If the reference was a negative one, the mother had a more difficult time accepting her infant (Rubin, 1967b).

Infants born ill or premature may not stay in the delivery room with the mother. The infant who requires intensive care is transported to the NICU, and an initial visit by the mother may be delayed by hours or even days. Delaying the interaction between mother and infant may result in problems with attachment (Pennestri et al., 2015; Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016). Due to the separation of mother and infant, basic actions of

attachment cannot occur. Limiting the mother's time spent with her infant can lead to inadequate attachment as the mother cannot spend time touching, talking to or caring for her infant (Feeley et al., 2016; Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016).

Maternal-Infant Attachment Challenges in the NICU

Bonding can be difficult for a mother and her infant when the infant is admitted to the NICU (Flacking, Thomson, & Axelin, 2016; Pennestri et al., 2015). The infant in the NICU is usually critical upon arrival and requires monitoring, intravenous lines and potentially endotracheal intubation. Particularly ill infants may have negative physiological responses to touch, such as oxygen desaturation or increases in heart rate or blood pressure. This can interfere with the development of the maternal-infant bond (Feeley, Genest, Niela-Vilen, Charbonneau, & Axelin, 2016). Feeley et al. (2016) found that different forms of contact with infants in the NICU, such as talking, touching, feeding, and, if possible, skin-to-skin contact, will result in better outcomes for the maternal-infant bond. This qualitative study demonstrated how the nurses caring for the infants, viewed the importance of allowing mothers to perform as much care as possible. Based on the infant's status as the infant recovers, the mother should become more involved with the physical care of her infant (Feeley et al., 2016).

In a longitudinal study conducted by Pennestri et al. (2015), 162 mother-infant dyads were evaluated to determine the quality of the maternal-infant attachment bond of infants who were admitted to either the NICU or to the normal newborn nursery after birth. Infants admitted to the NICU demonstrated a notable difference in attachment and reaction to their mothers. The NICU infants were more disorganized in their reactions to their mothers. Infant disorganization was described by Pennestri et al. (2015) as an

infant's response to their mothers, with behaviors that were considered to be "incoherent or bizarre", such as crying inconsolably while mother is attempting to calm the child. The mother's behavior, in reacting to the infant, may be unpredictable such as using an angry voice or brusque touch, thus resulting in the infant's further disorganization. Once an infant is labeled as disorganized the infant continues to become more disorganized. Researchers acknowledge that disorganization results in an increased risk for future mental health issues (Pennestri et al., 2015). This study demonstrates the need to monitor and facilitate attachment within the mother-infant dyad for infants in the NICU in order to stop the progression of disorganization.

Some studies examined premature infants and their challenges regulating their behavior and forming attachments (Browne & Talmi, 2011; Gerstein et al., 2017; Zelkowitz et al., 2011). The fact that an infant is born prematurely not only predisposes the newborn to physiological sequelae but may also increase the risk of developmental and mental health problems as the child ages (Browne & Talmi, 2011; Gerstein et al., 2017; Zelkowitz et al., 2011). The degree of prematurity correlates to the likelihood that the infant will suffer multiple physiological complications. Some infants, born between 22 and 24 weeks, require intensive medical care for extended periods of time, which hinders their ability to attach or bond with their mothers. It is difficult to determine if a secure mother-infant bond will occur once the infant's condition improves (Gerstein et al., 2017). However, evidence suggests that addressing early warning signs, indicative of a lack of secure attachment, can mitigate later attachment issues (Gerstein et al., 2017; Shah, Clements, & Poehlmann, 2011). A study by Zelkowitz et al. (2011) determined that

parental education related to the care of the premature infant resulted in better attachment outcomes for both mother and child.

Understanding and being sensitive to infant cues can help mothers improve their attachment with their sick infants (Tryphonopoulos, Letourneau, & DiTommaso, 2016). Mothers can understand and anticipate the behaviors of their infants so as to firmly attach with them. Moreover, mothers of NICU infants may not always know instinctively how to promote bonding with their sick infant. Gerstein et al. (2017) conducted a six-year longitudinal study of 148 infants and their mothers who had been discharged from the NICU. The researchers examined behavior patterns of the infants as they became older. Based on their findings, Gerstein and colleagues concluded that premature infants who exhibited disorganization marked by poor mother-infant bonding were more likely to develop other psychological issues as they aged. There is a higher risk of behavior problems or difficulty with attention in school and poor academic achievement. Research has demonstrated that infants who are at a higher risk of insecure attachment and disorganization should be identified early and recommended for intervention (Fearon & Belsky, 2011; Gerstein et al., 2017). A mother who does not form an attachment with her infant can experience increased stress, which can then cause the mother to respond poorly or react inappropriately to infant cues. This behavior, in turn, will cause more irritability for the infant (Garstein et al., 2017).

The Neonatal Nurses' Role in the Assessment of Infant Mental Health

In assessing infants and their caregivers while in the NICU, the nurse must be able to recognize the cues that an infant or the mother-infant dyad are exhibiting. An assessment tool can help NICU nurses determine when to alert the mental health team to

address possible mental health issues among infants in the NICU (Fleury, Parpinelli, & Makuch, 2014).

Fleury, Parpinelli, and Makuch (2014) conducted a qualitative study in which they reviewed nurses' care of infants in the NICU. These researchers studied how nurses, in their efforts to care for their infant patient, interacted with the mother. This interaction puts the nurse in the position to detect problematic behaviors in the mother-infant dyad that can be addressed early. The nursing staff who participated in the qualitative study noted the importance and significance of their role in promoting mother-infant attachment.

Another qualitative study examined the experiences of the nursing staff in two separate NICUs in Canada and Finland (Feeley et al., 2016). The nurses were given smartphones to carry and document their observations of the parents who visited the NICU during their shift. The researchers examined the nurses' interpretation of the parents' activities with their infants. Nurses were asked to qualify the observed interactions as either examples of closeness or separation. Nurses also had the opportunity to assist parents in activities to promote closeness. Inevitably, another key finding in this study related to the fact that the nursing staff realized their importance in assisting parents and intervening to increase their closeness to and decrease separation from their infants (Feeley et al., 2016).

Increasing nurse involvement and understanding of the importance of maternal-infant attachment is paramount in supporting parents when they arrive to visit their infant in the NICU (Feeley et al., 2016, Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016). Assessment of the

maternal-infant bond is critical for early recognition of maladaptive behaviors and early referral to psychologists.

Neurobehavioral Scales and Assessment

The Newborn Behavioral Assessment Scale (NBAS) was developed in 1973 and is still used today (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011). Brazelton studied newborns and examined the individualized differences with each infant's behavior. His observations also included his attempt to understand the mother-infant dyad and their early interactions. Brazelton noted that infants were not only able to interact with their environment but also with environmental stimuli. He theorized that healthy infants are interactive, social, and able to adapt to their environment. This led to the development of the NBAS screening tool to measure adaptive and interactive behaviors (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011).

The NBAS measures an infant's behavior in several areas that provide an overall index of the newborn's abilities (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011). One of the areas that is measured is the infant's ability to self-regulate and to show attachment to the caregiver, such as "en face" eye contact with mother, calming with mother's soothing voice, and calming with gentle touching. These attributes are linked to positive mental health. Conversely, infants who display difficulty with self-regulation and poor attachment are thought to be at risk for future mental health problems (Gerstein et al., 2017).

The Neonatal Intensive Care Unit Network Neurobehavioral Scale (NNS) is another tool that is utilized to identify newborns at risk for future behavior problems, continued illness, physiological problems and feeding issues that can affect infants as they mature (Boukydis, Bigsby, & Lester, 2004). This tool is useful for assessing premature infants as well as full-term infants who are considered at risk for future mental

health issues. The NNNS is useful for identification of neurological, motor, or developmental problems that the infant may be exhibiting, thus facilitating early referral for rapid intervention to ameliorate poor mental health (Boukydis, Bigsby, & Lester, 2004).

The NNNS looks at factors of habituation, attention, arousal, and regulation in infants among other variables. This instrument has been deemed a reliable and valid tool that can be used to evaluate neurobehavior in premature infants in the NICU. Fink, Tronick, Olson & Lester (2012) evaluated the NNNS for internal consistency and noted the Cronbach's alpha ranged from 0.87 to 0.90.

In a study by Brown et al. (2009), premature infants were tested using both brain imaging and the NNNS. The results of both tests were consistent with a neurological deficit, with the brain scan showing decreased brain sizes in patients who scored lower. Another study compared the NNNS tool results for infants diagnosed with congenital heart disease with the results of normal neonates. The results confirmed that infants with congenital heart disease were at a higher risk of developing neurobehavioral problems such as stress, attention and self-regulation difficulties (Hogan et al., 2018).

Summary

The attachment of a mother and her infant is a significant factor in the mental health of both the mother and the infant. A secure attachment is also an important facet in the development of a healthy relationship between the mother and her infant (Bowlby, 1988). Mother and infant portray characteristics of attachment when they interact with each other, particularly in the period immediately after birth. The interactions between

mother and infant are important to strengthen the bond between the dyad as time progresses (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011).

In times when separation does not allow the attachment process to occur, such as admission to the neonatal intensive care unit, there will be a disturbance in the attachment. Nurses must work with the mother to involve her in the care of her infant. When the mother is not able to bond with her infant, intervention from a mental health professional must occur. Early intervention is a key factor in assisting the mother-infant attachment process and ultimately promoting a healthy attachment for the mother-infant dyad to prevent the risk of future mental health issues for the mother and/or her infant.

Infants admitted to the NICU are at higher risk of inadequate maternal-infant attachment and will require assistance from the providers in the NICU to allow for bonding to occur as early as possible. The early intervention from the healthcare team can make a difference in encouraging positive mental health for the mother and her infant.

METHODS

This methods section describes the design, setting, procedures, sample, measures, and ethical considerations used for this project. The use of the (PDSA) model guided the process of this quality improvement (QI) project in the development of a protocol for a nurse driven assessment of maternal-infant attachment behaviors in order to increase awareness and knowledge of maternal-infant attachment and increase patient referrals to the psychology team.

Design

The goal of this quality improvement project was to create a guide for nurses to identify both positive and negative indicators of the maternal-infant bond in order to initiate early mental health referrals. This involved the development of a nurse driven assessment tool, testing the tool for inter-rater reliability when used in the clinical setting followed by collection of data generated by a specified pilot testing period and ending with an analysis of the data to evaluate its effectiveness in assisting nurses in identification of poor maternal-infant bonding dyads.

Ethical Considerations

A letter of approval from the project hospital was obtained. The project was submitted for Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval at the project hospital and California State University, Long Beach and was approved by both groups (Appendix B and Appendix C, respectively).

Setting

The project took place in a level IV NICU, at a magnet designated children's hospital located in Los Angeles. The unit has a total of 58 critical care beds with 244

registered nurses (RNs) caring for these infants. The patient population was comprised of infants, who were admitted for a higher level of care or a surgical intervention that was not available at their birth hospital. The NICU is also a center for total body cooling, and ECMO, which are highly specialized therapies for critical infants.

The unit is divided into five zones with each zone having infants of various diagnoses and acuity levels. The placement of an infant in a zone is decided upon by the NICU charge nurse based on bed space, staffing and acuity of each zone. The zone designated for this project is called Zone One, which consists of 11 NICU beds and 6 to 11 RNs providing nursing care for these infants. The number of RNs in the zone was dependent on the acuity of the infants.

All infants in Zone One were included in the project except for those infants who were intubated, on ventilatory support, medically paralyzed, on ionotropic or sedative medications, on cooling protocol or EEG monitoring. The biological mother of the infant was included in the assessment or a maternal guardian if the mother could not visit her infant.

Sample

At the time of this project the hospital employed 247 RNs who worked in the NICU as bedside nurses. All RNs who worked in Zone One during the pilot time were included in the education provided regarding the nurse driven assessment. Because RNs are rotated throughout the entire unit, 150 nurses were provided the education involving the nurse driven assessment. Of the 150 RNs, there was one master's prepared nurse, 147 bachelor's prepared nurses, and three associate degree nurses. There were 80 nurses who worked full time, 43 nurses worked part time, and two nurses worked per diem; they

were all regular employees of the hospital. In addition, there were a total of 25 travel nurses, included in the full-time employees, who were contracted with the hospital through an outside agency. All nurses who are employed by the hospital or brought in as contracted nurses, are trained to care for all patients, apart from those infants requiring care from specialty nurses, such as RNs working as members of ECMO or continuous renal replacement therapy teams. The nursing ratio throughout the unit was one RN to one patient, or one RN to two patients. There were a few occasions when the acuity of the patient required two RNs.

Procedure

Tool Development

Development of the tool began with the expert panel compiling a list of both infant attachment and maternal bonding characteristics that indicate behaviors from either mother or infant of negative or positive attachment and bonding. The panel was given a list of characteristics and from that list chose the characteristics that they believed were the most common. The first list was determined using inter-rater agreement of 90%. The final list included the characteristics agreed upon by all panel members. The initial list of characteristics was derived from the studies by Brazelton and Nugent (2011), Browne and Talmi (2011), and Phuma-Ngaiyaye and Kalembo (2016). These characteristics have been identified as associated with mother-infant interactions. The following are behavioral cues that may be exhibited by the infant that were given to the expert panel for initial discussion and potential inclusion in the final NDA tool.

Positive infant attachment behaviors include:

- notable gaze of infant to mother in the “en face” position, if able to hold infant and interact with infant (Brazelton and Nugent 2011).
- smiling back at mother as she smiles at and talks to her infant (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011; Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016),
- cooing, responding to mother’s cooing or talking to infant (Brazelton & Nugent 2011).

Negative behaviors that may be exhibited by the infant are:

- crying inconsolably when mother is there and attempting to soothe infant (Gerstein et al., 2017)
- no eye contact with mother, despite mother’s attempts to gain the attention of the infant and make eye contact (Gerstein et al., 2017; Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016)
- irritability and inconsolability when mother is softly stroking or touching infant in an attempt to calm or soothe infant (Gerstein et al., 2017; Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016)

There are also positive and negative behaviors that may be noted from the mother that can impact maternal-infant bonding (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011; Gerstein et al., 2017; Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016). Positive behaviors that may occur when the mother is with her infant and initiates the following:

- touching infant in a soothing or calming manner (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011).
- holding infant in her arms, close to her body, if possible; skin to skin contact when possible and comfortable (Brazelton & Nugent, 2011; Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016).

- talking or singing to infant in a soothing manner (Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016).
- asking to participate in the basic care of the infant such as changing diapers or assisting with sponge bath (Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016).

Examples of negative behaviors that may occur and may impede the maternal-infant bond are:

- sits or stands at bedside with no interest or appears fearful of touching infant (Gerstein et al., 2017; Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016).
- noted to be distracted from interacting with her infant, such as looking at cell phone or talking to visitors who may be with her and not paying any attention to infant (Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016).
- limited or rushed visitation such as only visiting 30 minutes at a time, or no visitation at all (Phuma-Ngaiyaye & Kalembo, 2016).
- talking loudly or angrily to infant; and looks sad, crying inappropriately, such as spontaneous crying, despite positive progress of the infant (Gerstein et al., 2017).

The tool included other characteristics suggested and determined by the panel to be more indicative of maternal-infant attachment. An agreement of 100% by all the panel members was required to include the characteristic in the final tool. During the first meeting, there was not 100% agreement with each characteristic (see Appendix D). The panel met for a second review of characteristics that would be included in the tool and at this time, there was 100% agreement with all members of the panel (see Appendix E). The format of the tool was discussed and agreed upon to provide the final version of the tool that was used for the assessment of the maternal-infant attachment (see Appendix F).

A data collection excel file was developed to record information on the number of eligible infants and NDAT tools distributed and completed per week (see Appendix G).

Inter-Rater Reliability of Nurse Driven Assessment Tool

The assessment tool was named the Nurse Driven Assessment Tool (NDAT), The project author recruited and trained four super users, two on day shift and two on night shift. The super users were nurses who were part of the expert panel that selected the characteristics used in the tool. The super users were trained two weeks prior to the staff who participated in the pilot of the tool. The super users also assisted in the inter-rater reliability testing of the tool in the zone, prior to the beginning of the pilot implementation of the tool. The project author developed a tool to score inter rater reliability for the assessment (see Appendix H).

In order to determine inter rater reliability the super users observed a mother - infant interaction and used the NDAT to score the observation. The project author was present and conducted an assessment using the tool to assess same dyad that the super user assessed. The two scores were compared, and both the maternal and infant scores had to have 80% agreement between the super user and the project author. A score of 80% was selected as the goal to demonstrate satisfactory inter-rater reliability agreement.

The super user's scores on the NDAT were compared to the results of the project author each time a comparison observation was done. Each of the four super users had a percentage agreement of 100% to 75% in assessing the characteristics of the mother. The infant characteristics were more difficult to agree on as there were at total of seven infant characteristics. The agreement of the infant's characteristics between the project author and super user was approximately 80% to 62.5%. When the super user did not have at

least 80% agreement on the NDAT tool comparison, re-education was provided at that time. If the super user had questions regarding the use of the NDAT, they were answered. There was an issue with the differences in assessment of the infant characteristics. This will be considered with further use of the NDAT tool. Once the super users obtained at least 80% agreement with the use of the NDAT, they became the trainers for implementation of the NDAT in the zone and were also available for questions that the staff had while completing the NDAT.

In order for a staff nurse to work independently, users of the NDAT had to have inter-rater reliability scores of 80% with the project author and or one of the super user partners. If a score of 80% was not achieved, the users were retrained on the use of the NDAT during their shift and inter-rater reliability was again re-evaluated with a super user. When inter-rater reliability testing was done with staff at week one, two, and three of the project implementation, agreement scores were 75% or higher when compared to super users' and the project author's scores. Education was provided to staff who had an agreement score lower than 80%. This education ensured that the NDAT was being used as intended. Consistent with the super users, agreement on the characteristics of the infant were found to have less inter-rater reliability among staff with a typically score of 65%. This discrepancy may have been due to the number of choices that were provided on the NDAT.

Education Plan

An education plan was devised in conjunction with members of the expert panel to ensure the knowledge and criteria required for implementation of the NDAT was presented (Appendix I). The education included a discussion of the importance of the

assessment of maternal-infant attachment for recognizing problems in the maternal-infant bond and facilitating a referral to the mental health team.

The education consisted of the following content and topics:

- The project purpose and objectives of the project.
- Overview of maternal-infant bonding.
- The recognition of the positive and negative characteristics of maternal-infant attachment.
- The use of the EMR for documentation of the maternal characteristics of attachment that are not currently noted in the current EMR format.
- Real time examples, with current patients
- How to use and score the NDAT.
- The use of the assessment tool to request an early referral to social work for psychological intervention, based on the results of the assessment tool.

The education was provided to the NICU nursing staff who were assigned to Zone One for each shift. The education included how to use the tool and what the expectations were for the bedside nurse of each infant and mother. The education session involved a discussion as well as a question and answer period. Several sessions were conducted during the zone huddle at the beginning of each shift. Sessions were held in the zone, as soon as all staff had received change of shift report from the previous shift. If the nurse was unavailable for the zone huddle, education was completed with the nurse, once they became available.

During the zone huddle, a brief discussion of the importance of maternal-infant attachment and the possibilities of issues developing later in life if the maternal-infant

attachment is interrupted and a bond is not formed. The staff was queried as to whether they had prior knowledge of the psychology team that is available for the patients and families in the NICU. A brief review of the current documentation of visitor and visitor interaction was done in order to realize the lack of a complete interaction assessment that is available to the nurse for recording maternal-infant interaction. Finally, the NDAT was discussed and reviewed, using an example of a familiar infant and mother in the zone to demonstrate the proper way to complete the tool.

Implementation of the NDAT

The next step in the project was to implement the process. The tool was placed at each bedside of those infants whose mothers were included in the assessment. The tool was provided for both day and night shifts. The tools were placed inside the infant's white chart, located at the bedside for each infant, by eight o'clock in the morning. Each NDAT was coded by the project author prior to distribution and was placed in the bedside chart by the project author each day of the week.

Each form had a unique identifying number between 0001 to 0029. This number was linked with the name of the infant. This information was maintained on a separate log book that was kept in a locked cabinet, in the project author's office. This coding process was completed prior to distribution of the NDAT in order to maintain anonymity of the patient.

The NDAT was collected by the project author, each day by eight o'clock. Tools completed over the weekend were collected on Mondays during rounds. On the weekends, the NDAT remained in the patient's bedside chart so that they could be collected on Monday morning. Although the name was not provided on the assessment

form, the log contained the patient's name in order to determine if and when the patient was referred to the psychology team.

Review of the NDAT

The project author reviewed the tools daily, Monday through Friday, for accuracy and for any possible issues that were noted by the bedside staff. At the end of the 30-day pilot, all forms were reviewed together, and the information gathered was synthesized. There was a distribution of 651 tools with 460 tools completed, indicating a completion rate of 70.66%. If there was documentation of troublesome behavior on the NDAT, it was noted.

The project author was advised to contact the psychologists for total numbers of referrals that were made during the 30-day trial. Due to IRB restrictions, the project author was not authorized to access the EMR to determine if any of the patients in Zone One were referred to the psychology team. During the pilot, there was nothing noted on the NDATs that would have triggered a referral, however the nurses who used the NDAT commented on the usefulness of the tool and having the characteristics of maternal-infant attachment identified for them to refer to and note any deviations in the attachment process.

Evaluation of the NDAT

A survey was created to evaluate the education of the project and the appropriate use of the tool (see Appendix J). A list of staff who had been assigned to Zone One during the 30-day pilot was compiled in order to send the survey to the appropriate staff. The survey was distributed seven, fourteen and twenty-one days after the completion of the pilot via email by the nurse researcher who is employed by the project facility. This

was a stipulation of the IRB so as to avoid any suggestion of coercion by the project author since the project author is a manager on the unit where the project was implemented. The web link to Survey Monkey was provided in the email for staff to access the survey. The results were anonymous, and the project author asked questions of the NDAT and its use. No demographics were collected.

RESULTS

The pilot was conducted in Zone One of the NICU over 30 days using the NDAT. The NDAT findings and analysis were based upon the observed interaction between the infant and mother along with the nurse's comments. The tool revealed the number of infants who did and did not have any visitors during their stay in zone one. There were two infants that had no visitors during the entire 30-day pilot due to extenuating circumstances involving the mother. The occasional missed visit should not be taken as indicator of problems with attachment, since mothers may not have been able to visit due to illness or other family responsibilities.

Zone One is part of the NICU with a total of 11 beds. Over the 30-day pilot, 640 tools were distributed. The nurses completed a total of 416 tools, with 224 returned blank, this was a completion rate of 65%. There was a total of 29 infants in Zone One. All infants except two had visitors at various times of the day. The two infants had mothers who were not able to visit due to social issues leading to a hold placed from the Department of Family and Child Services and other extenuating circumstances that did not allow these mothers to visit.

The four super users who were RNs with at least 10 years of NICU experience were trained in the use of the NDAT, prior to beginning the pilot in Zone One. Each of the super users and the project author completed an NDAT observation on a different patient in Zone One. The results of each tool were reviewed and compared to determine inter-rater reliability. The goal was to obtain at least 80% agreement and if this was not reached, the project author reviewed the tool and provided further education on the NDAT. There were notable difficulties reaching 80% agreement with every observation,

possibly due to the number of infant characteristics to choose from. Overall, the project author and super user agreement was approximately 62.5%. This is an issue that will be considered with further use of the NDAT tool.

Once the 30-day pilot was completed, participating staff nurses were asked to rate their opinion of the ease of use and applicability of the NDAT. Nurse's education and awareness of the importance of the maternal-infant attachment were measured by gathering information from a survey regarding the use of the NDAT and maternal-infant attachment. The questions also explored the nurses' knowledge of the psychology team and their understanding of the psychologist's role in the NICU. The psychologists were interested in learning how many of the nurses had prior knowledge of their presence in the NICU, and what their role entailed as it pertained to the infants and their families.

Analysis of NDAT Findings

Nurse Perceptions

There were 125 nurses who were emailed a link to complete a Survey Monkey post pilot implementation. There were 23 (15%) nurses who completed the survey. The link was emailed on three separate occasions in an attempt to obtain more participation from the nurses. However, the number of nurses who participated in the online survey remained the same. Each question and corresponding results are depicted in the following graphs.

The majority of the NICU nurses (91.3%) reported that the purpose of the project and the education were clearly presented and explained (see Figure 2) and 4.3% of nurses reported that the information, purpose and education were either not adequate or

somewhat adequate. The survey included the opportunity to provide comments or feedback; however, there were no comments.

Figure 2. Explanation of project purpose.

All 23 respondents (100%) reported that the tool was easy to use (see Figure 3).

The nurses reported positive comments regarding the use of the tool (see Table 1).

Figure 3. Ease of tool.

Table 1

Statements from Staff Nurses

Please provide any other comments or concerns regarding the education or use of the tool that may assist in this project.

I think the tool is easy to understand and practical to use

I think this is a good tool

Thank you for this education - mother/infant bonding is something we don't even highlight because it's so engrained in us as nurses, but in fact this education helps to highlight the fact that the mother/infant bond is important and needs to be assessed more closely.

I think it's really great that we're looking at the maternal-infant bond. It would be great to have more education about how the bond affects babies and moms later in life. It would also be great if maybe we had a care plan that we could start of altered maternal bond- we only have a parental one because then we could DARP on it and document more.

Note: Direct quotes taken from comments of participants

All respondents agreed that the information provided was applicable to their work (see Figure 4). The comments provided in the survey regarding the applicability of the information are noted in Table 1.

Figure 4. Applicability of information provided to the work setting.

The nurses reported having little knowledge of the role of the psychologists in the NICU (see Figure 5). The psychology team has been in the NICU for approximately four years, but many nurses were unaware of their work with NICU patients and families. Only 27.3% of the nurses were aware of the psychology team; 31.9% of the nurses responding that they were somewhat aware of their presence; and 40.9% of the nurses did not know about the psychologists' role in the NICU.

Figure 5. Prior knowledge of Mental Health Team.

The survey results indicated that the nurses needed education to increase their level of confidence about when to refer patients and families to the NICU psychologists for mental health services (see Figure 6). Of note, 73% of respondents stated that the maternal-infant bonding education helped them to know when to notify the psychology team if worrisome behaviors that required intervention were observed. There were 17.4% of the nurses who responded that they were somewhat able to refer an infant to the psychology team based on the information they received, and 8.7% of the respondents indicated that they were unable to use the information provided to make a referral to the psychology team. Additional education may be needed for some NICU nurses to promote

greater confidence in their role as patient advocate rather than assuming a dependent role related to initiating nurse driven referrals to the psychology team.

Figure 6. Assistance to alert Mental Health Team.

Finally, the survey was concluded with a request for any other comments or suggestions that the nurses could provide to assist in their future education and use of the NDAT tool. The comments are noted in Table 1.

Referrals

Although the number of specific referrals for zone one during the 30-day pilot was not available for review by the project author, the total number of NICU referrals during the same 30-day period was obtained during a meeting with the psychologists. Data on the overall number of referrals for one month prior to the project implementation were also obtained during this interview. Because of patient confidentiality restrictions imposed by the hospital IRB, the author was not allowed to analyze or report the NDAT information collected nor was she given access to the number of Zone One patient referrals during the project implementation timeframe.

There was a total of nine referrals from all NICU zones in the month of November, the month prior to implementation of the pilot project. In December, the month of the project, there were eight referrals from all NICU zones. In January, which was the month after the project, there were a total of eleven referrals. Although there was an increase in referrals the month after the project was completed, there were no data to explain the reason for the increase in referrals. The average daily census in the entire unit was 56.4 patients during each of these three months. The referral rate was approximately 16%, 14% and 19.5% in the months of November and December of 2018 and January 2019, respectively.

Review of the NDAT

The project author reviewed the tools daily, Monday through Friday, for accuracy and for any possible issues that were noted by the bedside nurse. There were no troublesome behaviors noted on any of the NDAT tools. At the end of the 30-day pilot, all forms were reviewed, and the information gathered was synthesized. There was a total of 191 tools that were blank and of those, 82 (42.9%) were from day shift and 109 (57%) were from the night shift. When separated by week, week one of the pilot had the most completed tools with 78.6% completed. Week two had 63.5% completed, with week three having the lowest percentage of completed tools at 56.9%. Week three was the week of the Christmas holiday, but there was no evidence to indicate that this was the reason for the lower number of tools completed. The percentage of surveys completed in week four was 65.5%, which was an increase from the prior weeks but not as high as the first week.

The tool contained items describing behaviors related to maternal-infant bonding, the presence or lack of which, could be assessed as a “red flag” signaling maladaptive behaviors. The behaviors that were assessed included four bonding characteristics reflective of positive maternal attachment behaviors. There were two infant characteristics, out of a total of seven listed, that could be deemed as troublesome behaviors indicating the need for referral. The characteristics that can be assumed to be a negative response would describe the infant crying inconsolably or an infant not responsive or not responding to the mother/visitor. Each of these two characteristics may be viewed as negative, based on the characteristics described by Brazelton & Nugent (2011); however, there is not enough evidence that these characteristics, when witnessed by the nurse, were actually a negative issue relative to lack of attachment. Due to some of the diagnoses of the infants in the NICU, inconsolable crying could be related to drug withdrawal or some neurological conditions.

Overview of the Results

In summary, the NDAT will need to be revised, based upon the results of the pilot. Some infant characteristics may need to be removed as the number of items was thought to negatively affect the inter-rater reliability of the infant scale. This decision can be made during the next PDSA cycle. The expert team will be consulted during the next cycle and a decision made after they have analyzed the results from the first PDSA cycle. The nurses used the tool to identify maternal-infant characteristics of bonding behaviors as part of their normal nursing assessment activities. Although actual mother-infant observations were collected by nurses in the NICU and characteristics of maternal-infant attachment behaviors were assessed, these data could not be used per IRB restrictions.

The information required for a referral would be any information noted to be indicative of a negative attachment behavior. Whether it be comments made by the mother, short visitation times, no visitation, without reason, or not interacting with the infant, by the mother, the psychology team should be notified for a referral. The tool itself was not part of the permanent medical record.

DISCUSSION

Assessment of the maternal-infant attachment needs to be a routine part of the NICU nurse's daily activities. This assessment can make a difference in the plan of care for the infant and the family. The education of the NICU staff nurses during the 30-day pilot accomplished the goal of increasing their awareness of the services of the psychology team available in the NICU. The NICU nurses who participated in the pilot, completed the NDAT based upon their observation of maternal-infant interactions. Based on the survey, only 6 (27%) of the nurses had prior knowledge of the presence of the psychologists in the NICU. Although the psychology team had been present in the NICU for at least four years prior to this project, there were many nurses who had no knowledge of their presence or their work with the families at risk for mental health issues.

The NICU is a 58-bed unit with a large nursing staff. The unit leadership hires approximately 30 staff nurses annually. The NICU employs an average of 40 travel nurses (16.2% of the RN population assigned to the NICU) per year, in addition to 207 permanent staff nurses. The NICU is staffed with many traveling nurses who do not stay long, this may be a factor related to the gap in knowledge about the services provided by the psychology team. The traveling nurses were not here when the psychology team was first introduced to the nursing staff and since their mental health services are not required by all patients, the more recently hired nurses may not have had any interactions with the psychologists prior to the NDAT pilot. This could be the reason that the staff who completed the survey were not familiar with the psychology team.

Project Limitations

An important limitation that may have contributed to the low survey response rate were the requirements of the IRB. As per their instruction, the project author was not permitted to send out an email with the survey link. The project author is one of the managers of the NICU; thus, the IRB did not want the staff nurses to feel coerced into completing the survey. The email with the survey link was sent out by the hospital's nurse scientist. The title of the email was "Invitation to participate in a survey about your recent maternal/infant attachment education." The project author's name was mentioned once when the nurses opened the email. During a subsequent conversation with a group of traveling nurses, at least 10 did not know the nurse scientist's name and five of them did not know that there was a nurse scientist at the hospital. In an informal discussion with other NICU nurses, the project author discovered that there were at least six nurses who ignored the email or deleted it, stating that they had seen previous emails from the nurse scientist which they typically ignored. Because there were only 23 surveys completed, it is difficult to generalize the results based on this low response rate.

Although the response rate of 23 was low, the responses were interesting. The nurses who completed the survey agreed that the education provided was applicable to their job. The survey also showed that they responded positively to the NDAT tool and stated it was easy to use. Developing a tool that would be easily used was planned in order to achieve compliance. The nurses completed an assessment on their patients and part of the assessment included the maternal-infant interaction. If the visitor was someone other than the infant's mother, this was also noted; however, for the purpose of this project, the focus was on the mother and her ability to bond with her infant.

Nursing assessment of maternal-infant attachment is an important part of NICU care as mothers-infant bonding is related to a child's future mental health. Preserving a functional family unit is a goal that involves all NICU healthcare providers working together in partnership. The NICU nurses care for extremely critically ill infants who may not be able to tolerate any type of touch or noise, which can be a challenging responsibility. For example, these nurses must determine when it will be beneficial or not for parents to begin to interact with their infant.

According to Flacking, Thomson, and Axelin (2016), a parent of an infant in the NICU may have a prolonged separation due to the critical nature of the infant's condition. Nurses are able to evaluate the separation or closeness of parents with their infant. Actions such as the decisions made to care for their infant were indicators of closeness. The NICU nurses play an important role in promoting the closeness of the parents in order to increase the ability of the parents or the mother to readily bond with their infant.

The survey results were congruent with the literature, in that the nurses play an important role in assisting the parents to interact and bond with their infants during their time in the NICU (Feeley et al., 2016). A few nurses verbalized the significance of their role in helping mothers bond with their infants, which the author found encouraging. The nurses now realize the existence of the psychology department and now view them as a resource.

The project author and the lead psychologist met to discuss the results of the pilot survey. The psychologist was encouraged by the results and agreed that there was a need for a formal education regarding maternal-infant attachment and their services. In

addition to educating the nurses about the positive and negative characteristics of maternal-infant attachment, there is evidence of possible trajectories that infants can follow if attachment is delayed or not developed. Based on the author's discussion with the lead psychologist, additional content on the subject of late effects of maladaptive maternal-infant bonding will be included in the next educational session that will be formalized and presented in huddles for the nurses as part of phase two of this project. This information will be added to the educational objectives, as this was one request that was made in the comments of the survey results. This education will also be provided to new hires in during their orientation. This will decrease the possibility of loss of information due to staff turnover. The educational evaluation tool will be revised and the process for distribution of the tool revamped to ensure a higher response rate.

The project author met with the nursing director for the NICU and discussed the results of the pilot. The project had been presented to the director previously, during the early stages of the pilot. The director indicated support for implementing the next steps of the project with the expectation that a presentation of the information will be provided to outside organizations, such as the pediatric and neonatal and associations, both locally and nationally.

Recommendations for the Future

As a consideration for next steps, the project author will request a modification of the IRB application and request to have the survey sent out at least one more time to the staff nurses who were involved in the initial 30-day pilot. Perhaps more information can be gathered with one more distribution of the survey. Additional comments from the

nurses may be helpful in planning for additional nursing education regarding the psychology team and maternal-infant attachment.

The education plan will be modified to a more formal process instead of using the zone huddle time, prior to their shift, to educate the nurses. There will need to be a discussion with all stakeholders in the project to develop a presentation that can be delivered during staff meetings. The nurses can be educated during their staff meetings since approximately 50% of them typically attend. The education should include examples of the characteristics for both positive and negative maternal-infant bonding by using pictures and videos to provide visuals to increase accuracy of identification. Using examples may also increase the inter-rater reliability because pictures can provide specific expectations for the types of interactions that meet criteria for attachment behaviors.

The PDSA model recommends that the cycle be restarted if the results of the initial cycle are not optimal or if there are sections of the process that may need to be changed to meet the needs of the project. In reviewing the results, the NDAT tool will need to be modified to include fewer characteristics for the infant. There were seven characteristics listed for the nurses to select from in identifying attachment behaviors. The difficulty in identifying behaviors may have been due to the nurse's interpretations of what they witnessed. This demonstrates the difficulties associated with inter-rater reliability as some of the behaviors that were observed left much room for subjective interpretation. This may explain the lack of obtaining an 80% inter-rater reliability score. The team of experts will be reconvened to review and make changes to the NDAT prior

to delivering the education on the maternal-infant attachment tool. The goal is to increase the inter-rater reliability score.

As discussed previously, the education should be more formal and should include the entire staff. Collaborating with the psychologists, neonatologists, social workers, and nursing experts, the education should be interprofessional. Evidence gathered during the research for the project will also be reviewed with the nurses. An interprofessional approach to the education for the nurses will provide more information and awareness of the importance of the maternal-infant attachment and the importance of early intervention.

As a long-term goal, the addition of the characteristics of attachment or infant reactions to maternal interaction will be added to the EMR. The nurses document characteristics that the mother or visitors display when they are at the infant's bedside, but at this point in time, there is no area in the EMR to record or document the infant's reaction. The project author, along with the psychologists, agree that if the nurses are able to document this information on a daily basis, the education that has been provided will be reinforced and can lead to a sustained awareness of the need for referral and intervention for inappropriate or inadequate bonding and attachment.

REFERENCES

- Ainsworth, M. D., Blehar, M. C., Waters, E., & Wall, S. N. (1978). *Patterns of attachment: A psychological study of the strange situation* (Classic ed.). New York, NY: Psychology Press.
- Ambrosini, E., Reddy, V., De Looper, A., Constantini, M., Lopez, B., & Sinigaglia, C. (2013). Looking ahead: Anticipatory gaze and motor ability in infancy. *PLoS ONE*, *8*(7), 1-9. <https://doi.org/doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0067916>
- Bohnenkamp, S., Pelton, N., Rishel, C. J., & Kurtin, S. (2014). Implementing evidence-based practice using an interprofessional team approach. *Oncology Nursing Forum*, *41*(4), 434-437. <https://doi.org/doi: 10.1188/14.ONF.434-437>
- Boukydis, Z., Bigsby, R., & Lester, B. M. (2004). Clinical use of the neonatal intensive care unit network neurobehavioral scale. *Pediatrics*, *113*(3 Pt 2), 679-689. Retrieved from <http://pediatrics.aappublications.org/>
- Bowlby, J. (1958). The nature of the child's tie to his mother. *International Journal of PsychoAnalysis*, *39*, 350-373. Retrieved from www.psychology.sunysb.edu/attachment/online/nature%20of%20the%20childs%20tie%20bowlby.pdf
- Bowlby, J. (1988). *A secure base: Parent-child attachment and healthy human development*. United States of America: Perseus Books Group.
- Brazelton, T. B., & Nugent, J. K. (2011). NBAS. Retrieved from www.childrenshospital.org/Research/Centers-Developmental-Programs/brazeltoninstitute/NBAS

- Brazelton, T. B., & Nugent, J. K. (2011). *Neonatal Behavioral Assessment Scale* (4th ed.). London, UK: Mac Keith Press.
- Brown, N. C., Inder, T. E., Bear, M. J., Hunt, R. W., Anderson, P. J., & Doyle, L. W. (2009). Neurobehavior at term and white and gray matter abnormalities in very preterm infants. *The Journal of Pediatrics*, *155*(1), 32-38.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2009.01.038>
- Browne, J. V., & Talmi, A. (2011). Family-based intervention to enhance infant-parent relationships in the neonatal intensive care unit. *Journal of Pediatric Psychology*, *30*(8), 667-677. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1093/jpepsy/jsi053>
- Crittenden, P. M. (2017). Gifts from Mary Ainsworth and John Bowlby. *Clinical Child Psychology*, *22*(3), 436-442. <https://doi.org/doi:0.1177/139104517716214>
- Cullen, L., & Adams, S. (2010). An evidence-based practice model. *Journal of PeriAnesthesia Nursing*, *25*(5), 307-310.
- Davidson, M., London, M., & Ladewig, P. (2008). *Maternal-Newborn Nursing & Women's Health Across the Lifespan* (8th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Deming, W. E. (1994). *The New Economics for Industry, Government, Education*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.
- Fearon, R. P., & Belsky, J. (2011). Infant-mother attachment and the growth of externalizing problems across the primary-school years. *Journal of Child Psychology-Psychiatry*, *52*(7), 782-791. <https://doi.org/>

- Feeley, N., Genest, C., Niela-Vilen, H., Charbonneau, L., & Axelin, A. (2016). Parents and nurses balancing parent-infant closeness and separation: A qualitative study of NICU nurses' perceptions. *BMC Pediatrics*, *16*, 1-13. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1186/s12887-0160663-1>
- Firestone, L. (2013). Disorganized attachment: How disorganized attachments form & how they can be healed. Retrieved from <https://www.psychalive.org/disorganised-attachment/>
- Flacking, R., Thomson, G., & Axelin, A. (2016). Pathways to emotional closeness in neonatal units - a cross-national qualitative study. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, *16*, 1-8. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1186/s12884-016-0955-3>
- Fleury, C., Parpinelli, M. A., & Makuch, M. Y. (2014). Perceptions and actions of healthcare professionals regarding the mother-child relationship with premature babies in an intermediate neonatal intensive care unit: a qualitative study. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, *14*(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1186/1471-2393-14-313>
- Gartstein, M. A., Prokasky, A., Bell, M. A., Calkins, S., Bridgett, D. J., Braungart-Rieker, J., . . . Seamon, E. (2017). Latent profile and cluster analysis of infant temperament: Comparisons across person-centered approaches. *Developmental Psychology*, *53*(10), 1811-1825. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/dev0000382>

- Gerstein, E. D., Woodman, A. C., Burnson, C., Cheng, E., & Poehlmann-Tynan, J. (2017). Trajectories of externalizing and internalizing behaviors in the preterm children admitted to a neonatal intensive care unit. *The Journal of Pediatrics*, *187*, 111-117. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2017.04.047>
- Gillam, S., & Siriwardena, A. N. (2013). Frameworks for improvement: clinical audit, the -study-act cycle and significant event audit. *Quality in Primary Care*, *21*(2), 123-130.
- Hogan, W. J., Winter, S., Pinto, N. M., Weng, C., Sheng, X., Conradt, E., . . . Miller, T. A. (2018). Neurobehavioral evaluation of neonates with congenital heart disease: a cohort study. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*, *60*(12), 1-7. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1111/dmcn.13912>
- Korja, R., Latva, R., & Lehtonen, L. (2012). The effects of preterm birth on mother-infant interaction and attachment during the infant's first two years. *Acta Obstetrica et Gynecologica et Scandinavica*, *91*(2), 164-173.
- Lester, B. M., Andreozzi-Fontaine, L., Tronick, E., & Bigsby, R. (2014, August 25). Assessment and evaluation of the high-risk neonate: The NICU network neurobehavioral scale. *Journal of Visual Experiments*, *90*, 1-9. <https://doi.org/doi:10.3791/3368>
- Murray, L., De Pascalis, L., Bozicevic, L., Sclafani, V., & Ferrari, P. F. (2016). The functional architecture of mother-infant communication, and the development of infant social expressiveness in the first two months. *Scientific Reports*, *6*, 1-9. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1038/srep39019>

- Pennestri, M. H., Gaudreau, H., Bouvette-Turcot, A., Moss, E., Lecompte, V., Atkinson, L., . . . Meaney, M.J., (2015). Attachment disorganization among children in neonatal intensive care unit: Preliminary results. *Early Human Development*, *91*(10), 601-606.
<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.earlhumdev.2015.07.005>
- Phuma-Ngaiyaye, E., & Kalembo, F. W. (2016). Supporting mothers to bond with their newborn babies: Strategies used in a neonatal intensive care unit at a tertiary hospital in Malawi. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, *3*(4), 362-366.
<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2016.10.001>
- Rubin, R., (1967a). Attainment of the maternal role. Part I, processes. *Nursing Research*, *16*(3), 237-245.
- Rubin, R., (1967b). Attainment of the maternal role. Part II, Models and referents. *Nursing Research*, *16*(4), 342-351.
- Schaffer, M. A., Sandau, K. E., & Diedrick, L. (2012). Evidence-based practice models for organizational change: overview and practical applications. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 1197-1209. Retrieved from www.wileyonlinelibrary.com/journal/jan
- Shah, P. E., Clements, M., & Poehlmann, J. (2011). Maternal resolution of grief after preterm birth: Implications for infant attachment security. *Pediatrics*, *127*(2), 284-292. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1542/peds.2010-1080>
- Szaniecki, E., & Barnes, J. (2016). Measurement issues: Measures of infant mental health. *Child and Adolescent Mental Health*, *21*(1), 64-74. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1111/camh.12105>

The W Edwards Deming Institute. (n.d.). www.deming.org

Tryphonopoulos, P. D., Letourneau, N., & DiTommaso, E. (2016). Caregiver-infant interaction quality: A review of observational assessment tools. *Comprehensive Child and Adolescent Nursing, 39*(2), 107-138.

<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.3109/01460862.2015.1134720>

VanderWeele, T. J., Lantos, J. D., & Lauderdale, D. S. (2012). Rising preterm birth rates, 1989-2004: Changing demographics or changing obstetric practice? *Social Science & Medicine, 74*, 196-201. [https://doi.org/doi:](https://doi.org/doi:10.1016/j.socscimed.2011.10.031)

[10.1016/j.socscimed.2011.10.031](https://doi.org/doi:10.1016/j.socscimed.2011.10.031)

Zelkowitz, P., Feeley, N., Shrier, I., Stremler, R., Westreich, R., Dunkley, D., . . .

Papageorgiou, A. (2011). The cues and care randomized controlled trial of a neonatal intensive care unit intervention: Effects on maternal psychological distress and mother-infant interaction. *Journal of Developmental Behavior in Pediatrics, 32*(8), 591-599.

APPENDIX A**PERMISSION FOR USE OF PDSA MODEL**

Pamela L Quick <quik@mit.edu> Apr
12

to me, Janine

Dear Dolores,

Thank you for your interest in reproducing the PDSA cycle by Dr. Deming in your doctoral project. I am happy to grant to you nonexclusive permission to reprint the figure in your forthcoming work. Please credit the reprinted figure to W. Edwards Deming in *The New Economics for Industry, Government, Education*, published by The MIT Press, © 1994 The W. Edwards Deming Institute, p. 132.

Please let me know if you have any questions.

All best,

Pam

Pamela Quick
Subsidiary Rights Manager
The MIT Press
One Rogers Street
Cambridge, MA 02142 USA
Tel: 1-617-253-0080

APPENDIX B

IRB APPROVAL FROM CHLA

Sep 28, 2018, 11:43am

To: [Dolores Greenwood, MSN, RNC-NIC](#)

CLINICAL SERVICES - CHLA

From: Rita Secola, PhD, RN, CPON

Chair/Vice Chair/Chair Designee, Children's Hospital Los Angeles Institutional Review Board

Re: CHLA-18-00417 [Dolores Greenwood, MSN, RNC-NIC](#)

Nurse driven assessment of maternal-infant bonding in the NICCU ([Nurse driven assessment](#))

NOTICE OF IRB EXEMPTION *WITH STIPULATION**

**Stipulation: Because the PI is conducting this study to fulfill an educational requirement, IRB approval from California State University, Long Beach (CSULB) must be obtained before research activities may commence. Upon receipt, please submit the CSULB IRB approval to the CHLA IRB via amendment.*

Review Date: **9/28/2018**

Document(s) Reviewed: iStar Application (dated 9/23/2018)
 Research Information Sheet [Item 24.4] (dated 9/23/2018)

The above-named study was reviewed by a member of the CHLA IRB. The study has been granted an exemption per 45 CFR 46.101[b][1] and [2].

Please note that this exemption is granted on the basis of the submission describing the research. Any changes or modifications to the study will require submission of an amendment application in order to complete the standard iStar application for research subject to regulation. If the changes to the protocol result in a change of review status to expedited or full Board review, standard continuing IRB review of the protocol will be required.

Children's Hospital Los Angeles is committed to protecting the rights and welfare of human research subjects in all human research which is: 1) sponsored by CHLA; 2) performed by CHLA faculty or staff; 3) performed using CHLA facilities; and/or 4) performed using CHLA patients or nonpublic information about CHLA patients. The IRB is organized and operates according to Federal regulations (45 CFR 46 and 21 CFR 56) and ethical principles. CHLA has negotiated a Federal-Wide Assurance (00001914) with the Office for Human Research Protections and operates according to California regulations.

APPENDIX C

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS

DATE: October 25, 2018

TO: Dolores Greenwood, MSN

FROM: CSULB IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1329373-1] Nurse Driven Assessment of Maternal - Infant Attachment in the Neonatal

Intensive Care Unit

REFERENCE #: 19-111 SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

REVIEW TYPE: Administrative Review

ACTION: ACKNOWLEDGED EFFECTIVE DATE: October 25, 2018

Thank you for submitting the New Project materials for this Quality Assurance/Quality

Improvement project. The California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board has ACKNOWLEDGED your submission. No further action on submission 1329373-1 is required at this time. The following items are acknowledged in this submission:

- Advertisement - 18-00417 Recruitment Email_updated 9.23.18.docx (UPDATED: 10/9/2018)
- Application Form - content_orsp_irbapplicationforexpeditedandstandardreview_01-02-2018.docx (UPDATED: 10/9/2018)
- Letter - Dolores letterhead_CSULB School of Nursing (1)-1.docx (UPDATED: 10/9/2018)
- Letter - iStar acceptance of study.docx (UPDATED: 10/9/2018)
- Proposal - 18-00417 Research Information Sheet 9-23-18.docx (UPDATED: 10/9/2018)
- Questionnaire/Survey - NDAT evaluation tool.docx (UPDATED: 10/9/2018)

If any modifications for this project are required, please contact the CSULB IRB first, to seek approval prior to implementing the modifications. The IRB must confirm the modifications do not affect the risk/benefit ration for this project. If you have any questions, please contact the CSULB IRB

at (562) 985-8147 or IRB@csulb.edu. Please include your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review

Board's records.

- 2 - Generated on IRBNet

1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840 Ph. (562) 985-8147 Fax. (562) 985-8665

APPENDIX D

**CHARACTERISTICS OF MATERNAL-INFANT BONDING
FIRST MEETING**

Characteristic	Nurse Score	Expert Score	Agreement Y/N	Percentage
Talking or singing to baby	5	4	yes with added characteristics	100
Making eye contact with infant	5	4	Yes	100
Touching baby and stroking gently	5	4	yes with added characteristics	100
Holding Infant	5	4	yes	100
Calming	5	4	yes	100
Smiles	5	4	yes	100
Makes eye contact	4	4	yes	88
Coos	4	4	yes	88
COMMENT/SUGGESTION: Add negative behaviors for infant such as crying or looking away	5	4	Yes	100

APPENDIX E

CHARACTERISTICS OF MATERNAL-INFANT BONDING

SECOND MEETING

Characteristic	Nurse Score	Expert Score	Agreement Y/N	Percentage
Talking, singing, or reading to baby	5	4	yes	100
Making eye contact with infant	5	4	yes	100
Therapeutic touch such as: Touching infant with gentle pressure or stroking gently	5	4	yes	100
Holding and talking to Infant	5	4	yes	100
Calming or crying inconsolably	5	4	yes	100
Smiles	5	4	yes	100
Makes eye contact or turns away	5	4	yes	100
Coos	5	4	yes	100

APPENDIX F

**NURSE DRIVEN ASSESSMENT TOOL
NDAT**

Mother Characteristic	Independently	With nurse encouragement	None of the time	Not Applicable/Not observed	Infant reaction (Circle all that apply)
Talking, singing or reading to infant					Calming Makes eye contact Crying inconsolably Turns away Smiles Coos No response
Making eye contact with infant					Calming Makes eye contact Crying inconsolably Turns away Smiles Coos No response
Therapeutic touch such as: Touching infant with gentle pressure or stroking gently					Calming Makes eye contact Crying inconsolably Turns away Smiles Coos No response
Holding and talking to infant					Calming Makes eye contact Crying inconsolably Turns away Smiles Coos No response
Comments					

APPENDIX G

NDAT CUMULATIVE DATA COLLECTION

DAY	Eligible # infants	Total # tools	# Tool Completed	Referral date	Referred? Y/N	New Referral
1	11	22	18		N	
2	11	22	18		N	
3	11	22	17		N	
4	11	22	15		N	
5	11	22	19		N	
6	11	22	15		N	
7	11	22	19		N	
8	11	22	14		N	
9	10	20	6		N	
10	10	20	14		N	
11	10	20	18		N	
12	11	22	20		N	
13	11	22	15		N	
14	11	22	7		N	
15	11	22	9		N	
16	11	22	8		N	
17	11	22	11		N	
18	10	19	14		N	
19	11	22	20		N	
20	11	22	10		N	
21	11	22	14		N	
22	11	22	16		N	
23	11	22	9		N	
24	11	22	11		N	
25	11	22	17		N	
26	11	22	20		N	
27	11	22	20		N	
28	11	22	8		N	
29	11	22	20		N	
30	11	22	18		N	

APPENDIX H

INTER-RATER RELIABILITY TOOL

Characteristic	Super user score	Project Author Score	Agreement Y/N	Percentage
Maternal Characteristic 1				
Maternal Characteristic 2				
Maternal Characteristic 3				
Maternal Characteristic 4				
Infant Characteristic 1				
Infant Characteristic 2				
Infant Characteristic 3				
Infant Characteristic 4				
Infant Characteristic 5				
Infant Characteristic 6				
Infant Characteristic 7				

APPENDIX I

EDUCATION PLAN

The project purpose and objectives of the project.

- Increase the number of referrals to the psychology team.
 - Overview of maternal-infant bonding.
 - The recognition of the positive and negative characteristics of maternal-infant attachment.
 - The use of the EMR for documentation of the maternal characteristics of attachment that are not noted in the current format.

Instructed on how current practice is important for the recognition of normal or strained interactions with mother and baby.

- Demonstration of the proper use of the tool.

Reviewed the use of the tool by using the example of a current patient and mother describing the positive and negative interactions between mother and infant.

- The use of the assessment tool to request an early referral for psychological intervention, based on the results of the assessment tool.

Discussed how the nurse may consider a referral through social work to the psychology team if the nurse notices any issues or problems with the maternal-infant bond that could prevent attachment from occurring.

APPENDIX J**EDUCATION AND TOOL EVALUATION**

Please complete the following survey of the education you received on the project and the use of the Nurse Driven Assessment Tool (NDAT). Make one selection:

1. Was the purpose of the project clearly explained?

Yes/Somewhat/No Comments:

2. Is the tool easy to use?

Yes/Somewhat/No

Comments:

3. Is the information that was provided applicable?

Yes/Somewhat/No

Comments:

4. Did you have prior knowledge of the Infant/Family Mental Health team?
Yes/Somewhat/No

Comments

5. Will the information provided assist you in alerting the Mental health team of any issues that you notice?
Yes/Somewhat/No

Comments: _____

Please provide any other comments or concerns regarding the education or use of the tool that may assist in this project. **Thank you for your time in completing the survey.**